

Capacity for change of individuals: The effect of the employee's capacity for change considering the impact of IT risk management during a digital transformation.

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ABSTRACT

Current literature on digital resilience is more focused on the change capacity from the organizational perspective and/or how leadership affects this change capacity. There seems to be a knowledge gap about the capacity for change from an employee perspective.

This research will focus on the capacity for change and the influence it has on digital resilience from an employee level. Found literature mentions the individual perspective on several occasions, but doesn't give a comprehensive view on what factors from the employee influence this capacity for change and the impact this has on the digital resilience of an organization. Since digital transformation is an enabler for Digital Resilience, the research will look at the impact of the capacity for change of an employee, considering the impact of IT risk management in the process of a digital transformation.

Keywords

Digital transformation, individual/employee capacity for change, IT risk management.

INTRODUCTION

In an eruptive world, digital resilience is an increasingly critical prerequisite for corporate performance (McKinsey, 2022). This resilience is also related to the capacity for change, which is defined as a combination of managerial and organizational capabilities that allows an organization to adapt more quickly and effectively than its competition to changing situations. Current literature on digital resilience is more focused on

the change capacity from the perspective of organizations and/or how leadership affects this change capacity. There is little to less knowledge about the capacity for change from the perspective of an individual within an organization, which leads to a knowledge gap. Found literature mentions the individual perspective on several occasions, but doesn't give a comprehensive view on which individual factors influence the capacity for change of an organization and the impact it has on the digital resilience of an organization. Adding to that, a digital transformation can come with risks, especially when organizations have a low degree of digitization. Risk management supports companies in managing risks within an organization. Therefore, this research will focus on the capacity for change of an individual, considering the impact of IT risk management in the process of a digital transformation.

The definition of Digital transformation: A process that aims to improve an entity by triggering significant changes to its properties through combinations of information, computing, communication, and connectivity technologies. (Vial, 2019)

IT Risk Management is an under researched area and is often named in conjunction with Risk Management in general. IT Risk Management will therefore be seen as a part of Risk Management in general. The following definition is made: "IT Risk Management is the ability of organizations to identify and adapt to risks with IT, in the digital spectrum with regards to information security but also business and organizational threats". Security is, and will be seen as, an integral part of IT Risk Management and Risk Management in general. (Edirisinghe Vincent & Pinsker, 2020)

PROBLEM STATEMENT

Digital transformation has become increasingly important in the last few years, and more and more organizations are investing in it. Therefore it is important to have an overview of all aspects that are involved in order to achieve a successful transformation.

Organizations need to assess their change capacity before undertaking change initiatives. Organizational capacity for change is a dynamic, multidimensional capability that enables organizations to create or revise competencies to survive and prosper. The individual plays an important role in this change process which makes it interesting to look at the change capacity from the individual's perspective.

Adding onto that, within the change process, risk management plays an important role. Change has always been accompanied by risks that must be taken into account. Effectively managing change risk is a necessary "muscle" to reduce, prevent, mitigate and manage the challenges associated with the transformation without causing decision paralysis or stifling innovation in the organization. IT change risk is the risk resulting from the institution's inability to manage changes in IT systems in a timely and controlled manner, especially in large and complex change programs. The issue here is that it is still unclear what the role of IT risk management is within an individual's change capacity and to what extent it has an impact within a digital transformation. When this relationship is known, organizations can better support employees in dealing with risks, so that employees become more confident about tackling and solving those risks properly. As a result, effectively increasing and deploying the change capacity of individuals.

RESEARCH QUESTION

Based on the knowledge gap stated in the previous chapter the following research question has resulted: "What is the effect of the employee's capacity for change considering the impact of IT risk management during a digital transformation"

This research paper looks at what impact IT risk management has on the capacity for change of individuals during a digital transformation. Thus, other research sub-questions can also be derived, such as:

- What is the correlation between IT risk management and a successful digital transformation?
- What kind of impact IT risk management has on the capacity for change of employees?

- What impact does the capacity for change of individuals have on digital transformation?

The relationship between the variables in the research question are: the impact of employee capacity for change considering the effect of it risk management on the organizational capacity for change during a digital transformation.

Figure 1. Conceptual Model

METHOD

As mentioned in the introduction the research will focus on the capacity for change of an individual, considering the impact of IT risk management in the process of a digital transformation. A lot of literature about digital transformations can be found, but this literature is mostly focused on an organizational level and not on an individual level; the employee level. So by literature review the relationship between the capacity for change of employees (individual level) and the capacity of an organization to start a digital transformation needs to be researched. And after this the influence of IT risk management needs to be assessed to the previous relationship. This is done by literature review and 3 interviews at 3 different IT companies. In these IT companies, project leaders and managers were interviewed. The interviews discuss how they support employees during a change process. Because these interviews were conducted for another study, not all facets of the research questions of this study are discussed. However, the data is useful, because it looks at an employee's capacity to change and how an organization can support this. In this way, a link can be made between handles that an organization can provide and the use of IT Risk Management. In this way a relationship can be established between what is described in the literature and what happens in practice.

Literature review

In order to ensure that the articles are relevant to answer the research question, a number of requirements have been set up. All articles used in the study have to comply with these requirements. The requirements to be used when searching and using articles are:

- Must contain the following keywords:

digital transformation, IT Risk Management, Digital Resilience, Capacity for change of employees.

- A minimum of 10 references.
- Peer reviewed
- (Preferable) Has to have at least some citations. Although this is very useful, it is not necessary, especially when using very recent papers.

Analyzing articles

In order to get the right information from articles and to find it easier later on, the relevance and key findings of each article have been written down. Since the work was split up among the researchers, every researcher did this during the analysis. The main topic is split into different sub questions which in term will answer the main research question.

After the relevant articles were found, a discussion took place. In this discussion the researchers present their found findings and explain the relevance to the sub questions and the relevance to the topic of this research in general. If the other researchers agree that the finding is relevant, it is incorporated into the study, otherwise the finding has to be revised in some form or discarded.

The key findings of each article were summed up in a list for each of the sub questions. Each finding was then checked for relevance and correctness. In a later stage, these results were incorporated in the study in general, together with the results from the interviews.

Interviews

In order to eventually compare the theory of the articles with practice in order to derive a more reliable result, interviews were held with IT professionals in companies. By writing down the key findings, this can be quickly compared with the key findings of the articles.

As mentioned before, the interviews were conducted for a previous research. When analyzing the results, some key findings fit the problem statement really well. So not all results are used of this research, but only the ones that looked at the relationship between the company and the capacity for change (resilience) of an employee during a change process.

To find these results from the interviews a simple relevance check per subject in the interview was used. These items were then noted and further examined later on. The found items, including their respective context, were used in giving answers to the research questions. Although more reliable,

coding and thematization was not used in this research due to time constraints. The validity of the answers is ensured by the use of triangulation in answering the research questions.

To ensure that the information received is valid, the interviews held have to comply with the following criteria: The interviewee has to have experience in digital transformation projects, the interviewee has knowledge of IT risk management and/or risk management in general, and the interviewee has been involved in or led change management aspects of projects. The interviewee does not have to have a level of seniority as long as the criteria are met.

RESULTS (NOT FINALIZED)

The results of this research are divided into three different sub questions, which are all answered individually and then later combined to give a final answer.

What is the correlation between IT Risk Management and Digital Transformation?

Security is the cornerstone of digital transformation. Security in this context not only spans the IT domain, but has an effect on and involves the entire organization, since business objectives and digital objectives are intertwined. (Shahim, 2021)

Possible reactions from individuals associated with IT risk management policies are: Non-compliance is mainly due to the resistance towards Information Security policies. Changes associated with implementation of Security policies create stimuli for resistance. (Merhi & Ahluwalia, 2019)

Digital transformation embraces the digitization of the entire company, including its products and services and their value creation system by implementing different technologies. Companies digital transform in order to stay competitive. The changes that come along with this transformation will affect the entire organization. So human (employees), technology and the company are in constant interaction with each other. With a result, new risks that occur. For example, lack of employees' acceptance of new technologies. When these risks associated with a digital transformation are managed, this will have a positive effect on the speed and adoption of a digital transformation. (Menzeffricke, 2021)

Risk management serves to support companies in dealing with risks. The specific risk management approaches used are usually related to the type of risk, in this research it is focussed on the technical risks.

Digital transformation is a socio-technical challenge, because it affects the whole company. Organizations think the changes that occur during a digital transformation only affects the technological dimensions, but also the human side. (Menzeffricke, 2021)

What kind of impact IT risk management has on the capacity for change of employees?

Since IT Risk Management can negatively impact the freedom of employees in a digital sense, it might decrease the individual's capacity for change in the case of larger more conservative organizations (Wols, 2022). A survey among employees of a Dutch bank has shown that employees find support, clear information, room for personal input, involvement and step-by-step implementation essential in a change process. This survey used Caluwe's theory to test how employees view change and what they consider essential in it. The most important results of this study are;

- A change can only be successful if the employees are behind the change
- Employees must have room for their own initiative and input
- Clear knowledge of what needs to be achieved is essential
- People change when they see the purpose and meaning of it
- Organizations change successfully when people feel they are being listened to

When we look at IT risk management, it appears that most existing research focuses on employees' intentions to comply with organizational policies, based on the assumption that people make free choices and that their actions are voluntary. This is not quite the case in the real world, as organizations "oblige" employees to comply with established policies. Results from the study of Merhi and Ahluwalia show that employee resistance to IT risk management policies may be an important factor underlying the high levels of IT risk incidents reported in several studies (Merhi; Ahluwalia, 2019). Thus, the effect of IT risk management on an individual's change capacity appears to be negative.

What impact does the capacity for change of individuals have on digital transformation?

For digital change to happen successfully, it is important that employees have an appropriate mindset. This can be done by including employees at an early stage of a digital transformation, by imparting knowledge about new technologies (Peshl; Schüth, 2022) and by reducing the stress

level of an individual. A high capacity for change of individuals does not only benefit an organization, but also the individual itself (Mahin, 2010). A high capacity for change results in a higher level of life satisfaction and job satisfaction on an individual level. On an organizational level it creates a more energetic, motivated workforce that is open to change might be advantageous to the organization.

A way to engage employees early in a digital transformation and share knowledge about new technologies is by organizing seminars and training courses. Seminars and training courses are effective in creating an appropriate mindset. Seminars and training courses can be included, for instance, in change management initiatives, to promote employees' resilience and openness to change (Peshl; Schüth, 2022). Besides seminars and training courses, changing an employee's mindset can also be done by having a one on one discussion with the employee. The downside of this, is that this could take a lot of time in big companies. (Ooijen, 2022)

Another way to create an appropriate mindset during a digital transformation is to reduce the stress level of an individual within an organization. Currently, the literature only looks at stress and resistance as two independent variables, and that they are immediate and natural responses to organizational change. Stress is an inevitable part of daily living and puts strain on the body and mind. By referring to them as distress and eustress, or stress of satisfaction, Selye (1993) distinguished between bad stress and good stress. Selye recommended enhancing the eustress response in light of the potential benefits of stress on human life rather than trying to avoid stress, accepting its components (Mahin, 2010).

DISCUSSION

The research question is divided into multiple sub-questions who all describe a different relationship. First the relationship between IT risk management and a digital transformation. The correlation between IT Risk Management and Digital transformation is that improper management of risks can inhibit potential gain from digital transformation projects. IT Risk management should be an integral part of any new digital transformation project, since CEO's are concerned with data breaches (Schlackl, et al., 2022). It is important to look at the employee satisfaction in this specific relationship. A survey among employees of a Dutch bank has shown that employees find support, clear information, room for personal input, involvement and step-by-step implementation essential in a change process (digital transformation). Results from the study of

Merhi and Ahluwalia show that employee resistance to IT risk management policies may be an important factor underlying the high levels of IT risk incidents reported in several studies (Merhi; Ahluwalia, 2019). Thus, the effect of IT risk management on an individual's change capacity appears to be negative.

When solving this negative relationship the capacity for change of employees will increase. Particularly when it comes to the workforce, a high capacity for change by employees can be advantageous for both the organization and the individual. Employees have a higher level of life satisfaction and job satisfaction. And an organization has a more energetic, motivated workforce that is open to change might be advantageous to the organization. A more motivated workforce that is open to change will result in a more successful digital transformation (Peshl; Schüth, 2022).

So, for a successful digital transformation it is important to consider IT risk management. One can speak of well-implemented IT risk management, when employees know how to tackle a risk and there is a uniform method for this. Employees have certainty when it is clear what their work is, this ensures that employees are satisfied. Employees are satisfied with their work when they find support and receive clear information during an organizational chance.

As discussed, research has shown that many IT incidents occur because the policy on its risks is not supported by employees. It is therefore important that employees are convinced and included in the IT risk management policy, so that they have the right information to be able to do their work. This ensures that they are satisfied with their work, because employees have indicated that they find this important in a change process. Which ultimately also has a positive effect on the organization, because this is an interaction. It is often seen that when employees are open to change, so is the organization and vice versa.

The results emphasize the importance of involving employees in a digital transformation. One has to realize that any organizational change is a subject to change management. The change management literature is vast and has existed for several decades, so although digital transformation is something relatively new, change management is not and has therefore enough handles that can be used in such a project. This is perhaps one of the main pitfalls of digital transformations, since they are often treated as something completely IT related and are therefore not subject to general 'change management'; this is of course nonsense. IT related change still contains all of the regular project management and change management

issues, but adds the complexity of the IT field. It is therefore not only an organizational change project, but also an IT project.

CONCLUSION

This research gave various insights with regards to digital transformation and the influences of IT Risk Management (ITRM) and the change capacity of individuals. The key takeaways from the research are that IT Risk Management can have a significant negative influence on digital transformations, in the case that ITRM is overlooked. ITRM can influence the capacity for change, and then primarily the willingness to change. One can logically assume that the capacity for change influences digital transformation, since digital transformation can be seen as organizational change, although the research shows that there are more variables at play. It is a constant interaction between human, technology and the company, with a result that new risks will occur. When organizations look at Risk management when considering a digital transformation, they assume these changes only affect the technological dimension. However, as mentioned a digital transformation is a socio-technical challenge.

The research showed the complexity of change management, which is a very interesting topic. And a second interesting topic of this research was the kind of impact stress has on an individual with regards to change capacity. This was mainly found in the paper "A positive approach to stress, resistance, and organizational change" and showed that stress consists of two main components, distress and eustress. The paper recommended enhancing the eustress and to use the potential benefits of stress on human life rather than trying to avoid stress.

One of the roadblocks in this research was the little amount of literature on IT Risk Management. This topic is very much under-looked as it is often seen as a part of Risk Management in general, and there can be arguments made for that, but it does leave out the complex and technical nature of IT risks. Therefore, suggestions for future research are to explore the IT risk management part in depth and research what effect it has within an organizational change process.

To make this research in the future more reliable is to, first off all, further explore IT Risk Management, and observe more case studies of organizational change and specifically digital transformations. This research includes interviews, although these interviews can be seen as secondary data since the interviews were originally conducted for a different study, but aligned with this research.

Validation of this research can be done in

various ways: One way is of course replication, but this can be time intensive; another way is to check the various references and compare the findings and lastly one can look at different research papers on the same subject and compare findings, although this might be more difficult.

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